

Excited state properties of linear polyenes : Fluorescence, fluorescence probe and photoisomerization studies of donor-acceptor diarylbutadienes^ψ

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The excited state structure and dynamics of linear polyenes have been the subject of numerous investigations in recent years. This is because linear polyenes like retinal (vitamin A aldehyde) play crucial roles in biological photo-sensory and photo-energy transductions. However, a complete understanding of the excited state properties of linear polyenes and related photobiological processes is not yet available. In the last few years, we have carried out photochemical and photophysical studies of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes with specific focus on the question whether or not dipolar twisted excited states are involved in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes. Our approach consists of examining the effects of substituents and media on the singlet excited states of donor-acceptor 1,4-diphenylbutadienes. In this context, we have chosen donor-acceptor 1,4-diphenylbutadienes $[\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{R}_1]$, $n = 2$, R and R₁ are various substituents including CN, NO₂, COOMe, NMe₂, OMe] as model systems and investigated their uv-vis absorption, fluorescence and photoisomerization properties in organic solvents of varying polarity, 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures, and in micelles of SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100.

The uv-vis absorption spectra of the donor-acceptor dienes are not altered significantly by changing the solvent polarity. However, donor-acceptor groups present on the phenyl rings influence the absorption spectra as expected in terms of mesomeric effects. In contrast, pronounced solvatochromic fluorescence is observed in most of the donor-acceptor dienes studied. The dienes substituted with strong acceptor groups like NO₂ and COOR have been found to exhibit much red-shifted fluorescence, which is highly dependent on solvent polarity. Low-temperature fluorescence studies in ethanol-methanol glass suggest conformational relaxation in the excited state of these dienes. The fluorescence quantum yields of the dienes are generally low, particularly in polar-protic solvents. The dienes with strong acceptor group like NO₂ and COOR exhibit large dipole moment changes ($-\Delta\mu$, 20–28 D) upon excitation. Further, the solvatochromic fluorescence of dienes linearly correlates reasonably well with solvent polarity parameters such as E_T (30) and π^* . Time-resolved fluorescence of some of the dienes is characterized by single exponential fluorescence decay with generally increasing lifetimes in polar solvents. Irradiation of the donor-acceptor *E,E*-dienes yields the corresponding *E,Z*-isomer due to one-photon-one-bond photoisomerization of the chain C=C double bond lying close to the acceptor group. The photoisomerization quantum yield increases with increasing solvent polarity. The fluorescence properties of some of the donor-acceptor dienes have been employed to probing the microenvironment of micelles in terms of their micropolarity, probe solubilization site and critical micelle concentration. Both fluorescence λ_{max} as well as the fluorescence intensity can be used to probe the microenvironment of the micelles.

It has been inferred that the photoprocesses of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes initially involve formation of delocalized $\pi\pi^*$ excited state. In polar solvent, this state can have B_u^+ character, and being ionic in nature, it is stabilized by polar solvents and substituents leading to red-shifted fluorescence. In non-polar solvents, however, the excited state can be of A_g^- nature resulting in weak emission due to forbidden nature of the $2A_g^- \rightarrow A_g$ transition. Further, the delocalized $\pi\pi^*$ locally excited state (LE) can get stabilized by non-radiative methods to an intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) state. Depending on the polarity of the medium and solvent reorganization the ICT state can decay to a conformationally relaxed twisted non-planar state from which much red-shifted fluorescence can occur. The photoisomerization can occur from the polar configurationally perpendicular relaxed species (P^*) that can exist in equilibrium with the ICT as well as with the conformationally relaxed twisted non-planar excited state depending on the electronic effects of the substituents and the polarity of the solvent. Further, the mechanism of formation and involvement of such dipolar excited states in photobiological processes mediated by polyenes linear, particularly retinylidene polyenes, is also highlighted.

These studies have brought out interesting features of the structure and potential energy surface of the singlet excited state of linear polyenes and further provided new directions for the development of fluorescence probes as reporters of the microenvironment of organized assemblies.

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Introduction

The role of linear polyenes like retinal (vitamin A aldehyde) in biological photo-sensory and photo-energy transductions (e.g. vision and halobacterial ion transport) has aroused a great deal of interest in the excited state structure and dynamics of linear polyenes. The key step in these photobiological processes is the isomerization of a C=C double bond in the polyene chain of the chromophore. For example, in visual pigment rhodopsin (Rh) and halobacterial pigment bacteriorhodopsin (bR), absorption of photons by the retinal-protein complexes leads to *cis-trans* photoisomerization of 11-*cis* C=C double bond in Rh and 13-*trans* C=C double bond in bR initiating the process of

vision and energy transduction in the respective organisms (Fig. 1). The electronic structure of the retinylidene chromophore and how it changes upon excitation is of key importance in developing a chemical understanding of the photobiological processes the retinylidene polyenes mediate¹⁻⁷. Additionally, linear polyenes and related molecules have also attracted much attention because of their novel electro-optical properties, which may find applications in molecular electronics^{8,9}.

In recent years, a great deal of attention has been paid to understand the nature of excited states of linear polyenes and in this context extensive photochemical and photophysical studies of both the polyenes as well as of the protein-polyene complex have been undertaken. A large number of publications including several excellent reviews on the structure and mechanism of functions of retinal-based photoreceptors as well as on the excited state properties of retinylidene and related polyenes have appeared in the last two decades. As it is not possible to quote all the published work, citation of only a few reviews is made in this article. Excellent accounts of the structure and mechanism of functions of retinal-based photoreceptors and the excited state properties of retinylidene polyenes can be found in Refs. 1-3, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11-18. Despite such feverish interdisciplinary efforts, the exact nature of the excited states of these polyenes is far from clear. Consequently, the mechanism of functions of these polyene-based photobiological receptors is also not fully understood.

It is generally believed that absorption of photon by linear polyenes results into twisting of the C=C double bond yielding a perpendicularly twisted excited state from which the *trans-cis* isomerization products are obtained. In the photoisomerization of linear C=C double bond, it has also been argued that considerable charge may develop in the excited state upon twisting to a perpendicular geometry and zwitterionic intermediates can be involved in the photoprocesses of ethenes¹⁹. This phenomenon is known as the 'sudden polarization effect' and is considered to be an important feature of the photoprocesses of linear polyenes²⁰. Role of simultaneous twisting of C-C single bond as well as C=C double bond has also been suggested in the photoprocesses of retinylidene polyenes^{21,22}. Similarly involvement of twisted polar excited states in the photoprocesses of retinal-based photoreceptors has been proposed²³. However, the exact nature of the excited states involved in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes is far from clear, and further work is warranted to establish the role of conformationally (across single bond) and configurationally (across C=C double bond) twisted dipolar excited states in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes.

To further characterize the charge separated excited state and to provide a better understanding of the excited state potential energy surface of linear polyenes, we have

Fig. 1. The chromophore and photoreaction of (I) visual pigment rhodopsin (Rh) and (II) halobacterial purple membrane pigment bacteriorhodopsin (bR). In these pigments retinal is covalently attached to a lysine residue of the protein via a protonated Schiff base linkage. Photon absorption by Rh causes isomerization of 11-12-*cis* C=C double bond to 11-12-*trans* geometry with ultimate photobleaching of the pigment to generate all-*trans*-retinal and the apo-protein. In bR, however, absorption of photon causes isomerization of 13-14-*trans* C=C double bond to 13-14-*cis* geometry and in this case the Schiff base linkage does not undergo hydrolysis in the photoreaction. Several dark intermediates are involved in the photobleaching of Rh and photocycle of bR^{2,3}. The microenvironment of retinal Schiff base chromophore is believed to influence the photoisomerization dynamics of these pigments.

undertaken photochemical and photophysical studies of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes. Diphenylpolyenes [Ph-(CH=CH)_n-Ph] have extensively been studied as model systems and several reviews of the excited state properties of diphenylpolyenes are available²⁴⁻³¹. Diphenylpolyenes are studied as model compounds due to their close resemblance in electronic excited states to retinylidene polyenes with the added advantage of being easily prepared and handled. Besides, diphenylpolyenes are fluorescent at room temperature rendering them as useful systems to characterize the singlet excited states of linear polyenes using various techniques of fluorescence spectroscopy. Further, the phenyl groups can be easily substituted making these compounds suitable for studying the effects of substituents on the excited states of linear polyenes. The singlet excited states of diphenylbutadienes are characterized by two low-lying excited states of A_g and B_u symmetry, which lie very close to each other. The relative ordering of the lowest excited states is influenced by substituents and solvents, thus influencing the nature of photoprocesses (e.g. fluorescence and photoisomerization) originating from the singlet ππ* state of diphenylbutadienes. However, the exact order of these states is not clearly known. In some earlier studies of cyano and methyl substituted diphenylbutadienes it has been shown that substituents and solvents affect the distribution of photoisomers formed under direct irradiation conditions³²⁻³⁵. Recently, picosecond spectroscopic studies of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadiene compounds have been done and evidence for excited state twisted intramolecular charge transfer and bicimer states has been presented^{36,37}. Very recently, photoisomerization and fluorescence properties of donor-acceptor *p*-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)-*p*-cyano-1,4-diphenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene have been reported³⁸. The photoisomerization and quantum-chemical modeling studies of absorption spectra suggested the formation of two mono-*cis* isomers. In addition, catalyzed thermal isomerization of the diene was observed on reverse phase chromatographic material. Solvatochromic behavior of intramolecular charge transfer diphenylpolyenes including diphenylbutadiene compounds in microheterogeneous media of micelles and polymer matrix have also been reported³⁹⁻⁴³. Fluorescence and photochemical studies of some diphenylbutadiene compounds in solid state has also been reported⁴⁴. In solid state, the dienes show fluorescence, which may possibly be from excimer species. Direct irradiation of the dienes in solid state has been found to yield [2+2]cycloaddition product.

We have also carried out photochemical and photophysical studies of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes with specific focus on the question whether or not conformationally twisted intramolecular charge transfer excited states and configurationally twisted dipolar excited states are involved in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes. Our approach has been to examining the effects of substituents and media on the singlet excited states of

donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes. In this context, we have synthesized several donor-acceptor 1,4-diphenylbutadienes and examined fluorescence and *cis-trans* photoisomerization behaviors⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹. It has been found that solvent polarity and stereoelectronic features of the substituents greatly influence the structure and dynamics of the singlet excited state of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadiene compounds. The electronic nature of the substituent and solvent polarity can alter the relative positions of the lowest-lying ππ* excited states (A_g⁻ / B_u⁺) and change the shape of singlet excited state potential energy surface influencing fluorescence and photoisomerization dynamics.

It has been demonstrated that the photoprocesses of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes initially involve formation of ππ* locally excited (LE) delocalized, planar state. In polar solvent, this state can have B_u⁺ character, and being ionic in nature, it is stabilized by polar solvents and substituents leading to red-shifted fluorescence. In non-polar solvents, however, the excited state can be of A_g⁻ nature resulting in weak emission. Further, the ππ* LE state can get stabilized by non-radiative methods to a planar intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) state. Depending on the polarity of the medium and solvent reorganization, the ICT state can decay to a conformationally relaxed non-planar, twisted excited state from which much red-shifted fluorescence can occur. The conformationally relaxed non-planar, twisted excited state can be highly polar in nature and thereby getting stabilized in polar media. The photoisomerization can originate from the configurationally relaxed, polar perpendicular species (P*) that can exist in equilibrium with the planar ICT as well as the conformationally relaxed nonplanar, twisted excited state, depending on the electronic effects of the substituents and polarity of the solvent. The mechanism of formation and possible involvement of such dipolar excited states in the photobiological processes mediated by linear polyenes like retinylidene polyenes is also briefly discussed. Additionally, we have shown that the fluorescence emission properties of some of these donor-acceptor dienes can be used to probe the microenvironment of micelles in terms of their micropolarity, probe solubilization site and critical micelle concentration. Both fluorescence λ_{max} as well as the fluorescence intensity can be used to probe the microenvironment of the micelles.

In the following sections, details of photophysical and photochemical studies of donor-acceptor 1,4-diphenylbutadiene (DPB) compounds **1-15** (Fig. 2) are described. The dienes were synthesized from the respective aldehydes and phosphonates via Emmons-Horner reaction and characterized by usual physicochemical methods. The fluorescence and photoisomerization behavior of these dienes in a variety of media including organic solvents of varying polarity, 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures, and organized

assemblies of micelles have been investigated. Thus, the effects of solvent polarity and stereoelectronic influences of substituents on uv-vis absorption, fluorescence excitation and emission spectra, fluorescence quantum yield (Φ_f) and lifetime (τ_f), excited state dipole moment changes ($\Delta\mu$), and photoisomerization quantum yield (Φ_{PI}) have been examined. Fluorescence studies have been done at room temperature as well as at 77 K. The fluorescence wavelength maximum ($\lambda_{f\max}$) has been correlated with solvent polarity parameters like E_T (30), R , π^* , and Kirkwood parameters. The experimental details of these studies are available elsewhere⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸.

Diene	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅
DPB	H	H	H	H	H
1	CN	H	H	H	H
2	NO ₂	H	H	H	H
3	H	CN	H	H	H
4	CN	H	H	H	NO ₂
5	NO ₂	CN	H	H	H
6	H	CN	H	H	NO ₂
7	OMe	H	H	H	H
8	CN	H	H	H	OMe
9	NMe ₂	H	H	H	CN
10	NMe ₂	H	H	H	NO ₂
11	NMe ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H
12	NMe ₂	H	H	NO ₂	H
13	CO ₂ Me	H	H	H	H
14	NMe ₂	H	H	H	H
15	NMe ₂	H	H	H	CO ₂ Me

Fig. 2. Structures of donor-acceptor 1,4-diphenylbutadienes.

Fluorescence and photoisomerization of donor-acceptor diarylbutadienes

Fluorescence characteristics of substituted 1,4-diarylbutadienes :

Nitrocyano substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes : Among the nitrocyano substituted DPB-compounds 1-6, it has been found that the dienes with nitro substituents on the aromatic ring are capable of exhibiting dramatically red-shifted fluorescence emission due to highly polar twisted excited states^{45,46}. The absorption and fluorescence spectral data of 1-3 and 4-6 in solvents of different polarity are summarized respectively in Tables 1 and 2. While the absorption maximum (λ_{\max}) of parent DPB is insensitive to solvent polarity, mono-substituted dienes 1 and 3 bearing cyano group either on the ethylenic bond or on the aromatic ring show a very moderate red shift of ~5 nm in polar solvents. Diene 2 with *para*-nitro substituent on the phenyl ring shows a red shift of 13 nm in its λ_{\max} in going from non-polar *n*-heptane to polar dimethylformamide. Similarly, only moderate red-shift of ~10–19 nm, depending on the position of the substituent, is observed in the

λ_{\max} of disubstituted dienes 4-6. The maximum red-shift is observed for diene 4 in which the electron-withdrawing substituents are on the *para* position of the aromatic ring. The red-shift in the λ_{\max} of these dienes is attributed to the increased conjugation due to the presence of substituent on the *para*-position of the aromatic ring. The excitation spectra of these dienes are similar to their absorption spectra, except that the λ_{\max} of excitation spectra of nitro-substituted dienes 2, 4-6 are slightly red-shifted by about 5 nm.

Table 1. Absorption and fluorescence data for dienes 1-3 in homogeneous media of organic solvents at 298 K

Diene ^a	Solvent	λ_{\max} nm	$\lambda_{f\max}$ nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f
1	<i>n</i> -Heptane	344	406	344	0.031
	Dioxane	347	407	345	0.007
	THF	346	418	346	0.007
	AcCN	344	420	343	0.003
	MeOH	344	420	343	0.004
2	DMF	349	422	345	0.014
	<i>n</i> -Heptane	370	470	334	0.002
	Dioxane	375	495	389	0.006
	THF	374	508	383	0.003
	AcCN	378	574	377	0.274
3	MeOH	379	606	378	0.003
	DMF	383	567	386	0.295
	<i>n</i> -Heptane	341	421	340	<0.001
	Dioxane	343	421	340	<0.001
	THF	343	422	346	<0.001
3	AcCN	343	421	340	<0.001
	MeOH	343	419	342	<0.001
	DMF	349	424	348	0.002

^aDPB in *n*-heptane and AcCN : absorption λ_{\max} 315, 330, 350 nm; fluorescence λ_{\max} 360, 380, 390 nm; excitation λ_{\max} 331 nm; Stokes' shift 4000 cm⁻¹; Φ_f , 0.67 (*n*-heptane), 0.01 (AcCN).

Table 2. Absorption and fluorescence data for dienes 4-6 in homogeneous media of organic solvents at 298 K

Diene	Solvent	λ_{\max} nm	$\lambda_{f\max}$ nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f
4	<i>n</i> -Heptane	362	400	343	0.012
	Dioxane	368	463	351	0.001
	THF	378	485	384	0.001
	AcCN	374	539	376	0.078
	MeOH	375	588	377	0.003
5	DMF	381	540	385	0.148
	<i>n</i> -Heptane	366	456	370	0.001
	Dioxane	371	484	376	0.001
	THF	373	486	371	0.001
	AcCN	374	540	378	0.001
6	MeOH	375	557	373	0.001
	DMF	376	522	392	0.018
	<i>n</i> -Heptane	356	399	357	0.002
	Dioxane	364	430	384	0.001
	THF	366	473	383	0.001
6	AcCN	368	523	375	0.021
	MeOH	368	573	377	0.004
	DMF	373	517	385	0.045

In contrast to a very moderate solvent polarity effect on the λ_{\max} of dienes 1-6, marked influence of solvent polarity on the fluorescence maximum ($\lambda_{f\max}$), particularly of nitro-

dienes **2**, **4-6**, is observed. The maximum red-shift of 188 nm in the $\lambda_{f \max}$ of **4** (in *n*-heptane 400 nm and in methanol 588 nm) is observed when the nitro and cyano groups are on the *para*-position of the aromatic ring. In Fig. 3 are shown the fluorescence spectra of **4-6** in organic solvents of various polarity. The cyano group exerts a slightly destabilizing effect on the excited state fluorescent species in

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of dienes **4-6** in organic solvents at 298 K : (a) *n*-heptane, (b) 1,4-dioxane, (c) tetrahydrofuran, (d) acetonitrile, (e) methanol.

polar solvent. The Stokes' shifts of nitro-substituted dienes are relatively large and increase with solvent polarity. These observations indicate towards the polar nature of the singlet excited states of the dienes.

To further characterize the fluorescent state of these dienes, dependence of Stokes' shift ($\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$) on the solvent polarity has been correlated in terms of solvent parameters like Dimroth's parameter⁵⁰, $E_T(30)$ [a plot of $E_T(30)$ values of various solvents vs $(\bar{\nu}_{a \max} - \bar{\nu}_{f \max})$] and *R* scale⁵¹. When the empirical Dimroth's parameter used as a measure of solvent polarity was increased, $(\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f)$ increases almost linearly for the nitro substituted dienes **2** and **4** and the slope is markedly larger for these dienes in comparison to cyano-substituted dienes devoid of a nitro

Fig. 4. A plot of solvent parameter $E_T(30)$ vs Stokes' shift for dienes (Δ) **1**, (\circ) **2**, (\bullet) **4**.

group. A typical plot of solvent parameter $E_T(30)$ vs Stokes' shift ($\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$) for dienes **1**, **2** and **4** is shown in Fig. 4. The solvent parameter *R* is a measure of the sensitivity of the system to change in solvent polarity and its values for dienes **1**, **2** and **4** are mostly found to be negative and range between -1.33 and 0.05 . In general, an increase in the solvent polarity results in an increase in the value of *R* too.

Further experimental evidence in support of the polar character of the excited states of these compounds was obtained by calculation of excited state dipole moment changes ($\Delta\mu$). Upon increasing the solvent polarity, fluorescence spectrum shifts to longer wavelengths, though the amount of shift depends on the substitution and dielectric constant of the solvent concerned. This solvent polarity induced shift has been used to determine $\Delta\mu$ using the Lippert-Mataga equation^{52,53} : $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = \{[2(\mu_e - \mu_g)2/hca^3] F(D, n)\}$ where $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f$ is Stokes' shift μ_e and μ_g are excited state and ground state dipole moments respectively, $\mu_e - \mu_g = \Delta\mu$ (change in dipole moment), *h* is the Planck's constant, *c* is the velocity of light, *a* is the Onsager's radius,

Fig. 5. Lippert-Mataga plots for dienes (Δ) **2**, (\blacksquare) **4**, (\circ) **5**, (\bullet) **6**.

and $F(D, n) = \Delta f$ is the solvent polarity parameter. $\Delta f = (D - 1)/(2D + 1) - (n^2 - 1)/(2n^2 + 1)$ where D is the dielectric constant and n is the refractive index of the solvent. The Onsager radius for these dienes was approximately taken as 9 Å which is known value for similar DPB compounds⁵⁴. A typical plot of Stokes' shift vs solvent parameter Δf for dienes **2** and **4-6** is shown in Fig. 5. The $\Delta\mu$ (in Debye, D) values for various dienes obtained from the Lippert-Mataga analysis are as follows: **2**, 20.9; **4**, 19.7; **5**, 17.5; **6**, 20.5 D. The Lippert-Mataga analysis clearly demonstrates the solvent polarity sensitive fluorescent behavior of these dienes, which is further well-supported by the large excited state dipole moment changes observed. These fluorescence data mean that the fluorescent state is not the initially prepared locally excited (LE) state, and it is more polar. Such polar excited state can be formed due to intramolecular charge transfer (ICT). The scattering of data points in some of the plots in Fig. 5 can be due to other specific solvent-solute interactions⁵⁵.

These dienes show rather very weak fluorescent emission. In general, the solvent polarity and the type and position of substituent influence the Φ_f . In protic-polar solvents like methanol, the Φ_f are very low. Aprotic-polar solvents and electronegative substituents cause some increase in the Φ_f . Increase in Φ_f with increase in solvent polarity can partly be attributed to the possible state reversals of the lowest excited states of the dienes. Thus, in non-polar solvent, the fluorescent excited state can be of A_g^- nature. Since $A_g^- \rightarrow A_g$ transition is symmetry-forbidden, the resulting emission is weak. In polar solvents, however, there is reversal of states from $A_g^* \rightarrow B_u^{*+}$, which gives rise to allowed $B_u^{*+} \rightarrow A_g$ transition responsible for relatively in-

creased Φ_f . The present results indicate that the lowest excited state of these dienes is of B_u character. The B_u excited state being ionic in nature, is stabilized by the polar electronic effects of the substituents and the polar solvents and hence the red-shifts in the fluorescence. The magnitude and the trends in Φ_f are, however, not very clear. The fluorescence properties of donor-acceptor compounds are known to be influenced by solvent dependent singlet-triplet mechanisms^{31,56-58}. However, whether presence of donor-acceptor groups promotes intersystem crossings leading to the formation of triplets and hence diminished fluorescence in these dienes cannot be delineated only based on the present results. Thus, the reduced and varying fluorescence efficiency can also be due to solvent-polarity dependent state switching. Diene **3** with a cyano substituent in the chain has the least Φ_f . Apparently, the cyano group has destabilizing effect on the fluorescent excited state. It is known that considerable charge separation may occur upon twisting out-of-plane of an ethylenic C=C double bond chromophore during the formation of perpendicular species in the excited state²⁰. Appropriate substituents can stabilize the resulting dipolar 'perpendicular excited state'. This effect can decrease the energy barrier for the formation of perpendicular state facilitating *trans-cis* photoisomerization and diminishing fluorescence. The low Φ_f can be attributed to the enhanced stability of perpendicular dipolar species due to cyano group in the excited state. Thus, while the cyano group on ethylenic bond renders the diene less fluorescent by lowering down the barrier between the fluorescent excited state and the perpendicular (P^*) state, the nitro group on the phenyl ring makes the diene fluorescence efficient by increasing the activation barrier for the

Fig. 6. Fluorescence spectra of DPB, and **1**, **2** and **4** in ethanol-methanol matrix at (—) 298, (---) 77 K.

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formation of perpendicular (P^*) species. The aprotic polar solvents appear to affect the excited state of nitro-dienes much before the formation of perpendicular state.

A relatively higher Φ_f and large red-shifted fluorescence of nitrodienes (e.g. **2** and **4**) in aprotic polar solvents further indicate that the fluorescence originates from highly polarized excited state. Such fluorescent excited state can be formed due to conformational relaxation via single bond rotations and involving intramolecular charge transfer process. Thus, due to different electronegativities present in the dienes, intramolecular charge transfer can occur via the twisted nitro group, and the polar solvents can stabilize the charge transfer twisted excited state resulting in much red-shifted fluorescence emission. To demonstrate the gradual change of fluorescence emission with increase of solvent polarity, fluorescence studies of these dienes were further carried out in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures. When the water content was varied between zero to 70% in 1,4-dioxane, the absorption maximum did not shift for diene **3**, and shifted only by 3 to 5 nm respectively, for dienes **1** and **2**. For dienes **4-6**, the λ_{max} shift was respectively 15, 6 and 9 nm. The fluorescence shift was also not very significant in the case of dienes **1** and **3**. Thus, while no change in $\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ of **3** was observed when the water content was increased to 70%, only a moderate red-shift of 16 nm was registered in the case of diene **1**. However, dienes, **2** and **4-6** exhibited dramatically red-shifted fluorescence in 1,4-dioxane containing increasing amounts of water. Thus, 501 nm fluorescence of **2** in 1,4-dioxane shifted to 630 nm when 1,4-dioxane contained 70% water. Similarly, 463, 479 and 469 nm fluorescence of dienes **4**, **5** and **6** in 1,4-dioxane shifted respectively to 603, 613 and 605 nm in 1,4-dioxane containing 70% water. Thus, fluorescence is highly red-shifted as the water content in the solvent mixture is increased. Since the dielectric constant of 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures is known⁵⁹, $\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ of the dienes were plotted against the dielectric constant of the solvents to conclude that the $\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ of the dienes is governed by the bulk dielectric constant of the medium. The polar nature of the fluorescent state of dienes **2**, **4-6** is quite evident from these data.

The fluorescence studies of these dienes have also been done at 77 K in 1 : 1 ethanol-methanol glass matrix and the results are presented in Fig. 6 and Table 3. There is considerable change in $\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ and in the Φ_f of these dienes at two temperatures in ethanol-methanol matrix. In fluid environment, the dienes exhibit fluorescence at different wavelengths ranging from 418 to 600 nm depending on the substituents. However, in rigid glass matrix, the fluorescence occurs at lower wavelength in the range of 412 to 492 nm. The $\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ of nitro-substituted dienes **2**, **4-6** are most affected with maximum blue-shift in case of diene **2**. The Φ_f , however, increases in the rigid matrix at 77 K. The fluorescence spectra of these dienes at 77 K are characterized by well-defined structures. These observations indi-

cate towards the absence of any significant electronic and solvent effects, and molecular motions (conformational and configurational changes) in the fluorophore at 77 K. These results provide further evidence towards the involvement of conformationally relaxed intramolecular charge transfer, non-planar excited states in the photoprocesses of nitrodienes.

Table 3. Fluorescence data of DPB, and dienes 1-6 in 1 : 1 methanol-ethanol matrix at 298 and at 77 K

Diene	Fluorescence at 298 K			Fluorescence at 77 K			$\Delta\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ nm
	$\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f	$\lambda_{f \text{ max}}$ nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f	
DPB	375	334	0.018	379	334	1	4
1	418	347	0.007	412	328	1	6
2	600	385	0.003	492	403	0.288	108
3	420	339	0.001	424	339	0.520	4
4	576	387	0.005	480	398	0.075	96
5	569	379	0.002	480	400	0.022	89
6	567	391	0.005	484	400	0.055	83

DPB : 1,4-Diphenylbutadiene.

Thus, it can be concluded that singlet excited states of nitrocyano substituted 1,4-diarylbutadienes are dipolar and such dienes can exhibit fluorescence from highly polar, conformationally relaxed intramolecular charge transfer excited state. Owing to the different electronegativities present in the dienes, intramolecular charge transfer in the excited state can occur via twisting of the bond between the nitro group relative to the attached phenyl (i.e. twisting about the C-N bond in $O_2N-C_6H_4-$). Twisting of the C-C bond of the dienyl moiety between the rings is not likely as it will require a relatively larger volume of activation. Furthermore, large amplitude motion such as that which occurs at the beginning of a *cis-trans* isomerization is also unlikely as the time required for such motion would be too great for it to occur within a fluorescence lifetime.

Cyanomethoxy substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes : Cyano- and cyanomethoxy substituted diarylbutadienes **1**, **7** and **8** have been investigated for their absorption and fluorescence properties in homogeneous media of organic solvents and 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures. The absorption and fluorescence spectral data of these dienes in organic solvents of different polarity are given in Table 4. As compared to the parent DPB, the cyanomethoxy substituted dienes exhibit red-shifted absorption λ_{max} . The magnitude of shift varies with the substituents. In contrast to nitro-substituted diphenylbutadienes, however, solvent polarity does not significantly affect the absorption λ_{max} of these dienes. Among the three substituted dienes, the di-substituted diene **8** exhibits the maximum red-shift in the absorption λ_{max} , which can be attributed to the increased conjugation due to the presence of additional substituent on the *para*-position of the aromatic ring. The absorption and fluorescence data for these dienes in various compositions of 1,4-dioxane-water are presented in Table 5. The increas-

ing amount of water in 1,4-dioxane does not alter the absorption maximum of these dienes to any significant extent. Thus, in general, solvent polarity does not significantly affect the ground state of these dienes.

Table 4. UV-vis absorption and fluorescence data of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in homogenous media

Diene	Solvent	Maximal wavelength, nm			Φ_f
		Absorption	Emission	Excitation	
1	<i>n</i> -Heptane	344	406	344	0.003
	Dioxane	347	407	345	0.007
	THF	346	418	346	0.007
	DMF	349	422	345	0.014
	MeCN	344	421	344	0.003
7	<i>n</i> -Heptane	338	387	334	0.050
	Dioxane	340	399	337	0.019
	THF	341	418	337	0.009
	DMF	342	419	337	0.009
	MeCN	338	413	334	0.004
8	<i>n</i> -Heptane	354	399	362	0.008
	Dioxane	356	431	364	0.006
	THF	354	442	365	0.005
	DMF	350	488	371	0.009
	MeCN	353	484	362	0.003
	MeOH	352	482	364	0.003

1,4-Diphenylbutadiene (DPB): abs. $\lambda_{f \max}$ 335 nm, em λ_{\max} 375–378 nm (in *n*-heptane, dioxane, methanol and acetonitrile); Φ_f 0.222 (*n*-heptane), 0.052 (dioxane), 0.015 (methanol), 0.009 (acetonitrile).

Table 5. UV-vis absorption and fluorescence data of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures

% Water	1			7			8		
	λ_{abs}	$\lambda_{f \max}$	λ_{ex}	λ_{abs}	$\lambda_{f \max}$	λ_{ex}	λ_{abs}	$\lambda_{f \max}$	λ_{ex}
in	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm
dioxane	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm
0	347	407	347/362	340	399	337	353	431	365
10	346	417	363/351	338	417	337	356	435	364
20	347	419	363	340	417	336	355	451	363
30	347	419	363	340	417	336	356	480	363
40	346	421	363	339	418	336	356	485	364
50	344	422	363	339	418	335	356	487	364
60	344	422	362	338	418	338	354	492	364

In contrast to a rather very moderate solvent polarity effect on the absorption spectra, significant solvent polarity effects are seen on the fluorescence behavior of these dienes. In organic solvents and 1,4-dioxane-water systems, as the solvent polarity is increased, the λ_{\max} undergoes a red-shift. The maximum red-shift in fluorescence is observed for the disubstituted diene **8**.

The dependence of Stokes' shift on the solvent polarity is correlated with Dimroth's solvent parameter $E_T(30)$ and Kamlet-Taft π^* scale^{60,61} [a plot of π^* values of various solvents vs ($\nu_{f \max}$) of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in those solvents, Fig. 7]. It is observed that the Stokes' shift increases linearly with increase in the solvent polarity. The dienes show reasonable correlation with solvent parameters $E_T(30)$ and π^* with the following regression data: **1**, [slope = 32.25, linear correlation (r) = 0.8441, number of data points (N) = 11]; **7**, (slope = 45.45, r = 0.8366, N = 11); and **8**, (slope

= 128.57, r = 0.9139, N = 11). The slope in case of diene **8** is the highest as compared to other dienes. Similarly, when Kamlet-Taft π^* scale is plotted with $\nu_{f \max}$, linear decrease is observed with increase in the value of π^* . The observed solvent correlations are as follows: **1**, (slope = 8.10×10^{-5} , r = -0.8250, N = 5); **7**, (slope = -1.42×10^{-4} , r = -0.9052, N = 5); **8**, (slope = -3.91×10^{-5} , r = -0.9329, N = 5). The

Fig. 7. A plot of Kamlet-Taft π^* scale against $\nu_{f \max}$ of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in: (i) *n*-heptane, (ii) 1,4-dioxane, (iii) THF, (iv) MeCN, (v) DMF.

Stokes' shifts of the dienes in dimethylformamide are excluded from the calculation of linear correlation r in the plot of $E_T(30)$ vs Stokes' shifts due large deviations. The deviations from linearity in the case of aprotic solvents like dimethylformamide can be accounted in terms of net stabilization of the diene in the excited state due to specific solute-solvent interactions⁵⁵. These quantitative analyses of solvent polarity parameters reveal that the solvated excited state of the dienes is more stabilized in polar medium than the ground state.

The solvatochromic shift of these dienes were further analysed in terms of Lippert-Mataga analysis with the Onsager radius taken as 9 Å and change in excited state dipole moments ($\Delta\mu$) were determined⁴⁷. The $\Delta\mu$ (in Debye) thus obtained for dienes **1**, **7** and **8** are as follows: **1**, 13.0; **7**, 13.6; **8**, 21.3. A rather large change in dipole moment upon excitation of diene **8** is noteworthy and it indicates that its fluorescent state is highly polar in nature.

As compared to parent unsubstituted DPB, the substituted dienes show relatively small Φ_f in organic solvents. The fluorescence efficiency of dienes **7** and **8** is generally decreased in polar solvents. The decrease in fluorescence efficiency as the substitution takes place suggests increased non-radiative transitions in the photoprocesses of diphenylbutadienes.

Similar to the results obtained in case of nitrodiene, the $\lambda_{f \max}$ of dienes **1** and **8** get blue-shifted in ethanol-methanol glass at 77 K (Table 6). Fig. 8 shows fluores-

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cence of dienes **7** and **8** at 77 K and at 298 K. The blue-shift is more pronounced (42 nm) in diene **8** bearing the cyano as well as the methoxy group on the phenyl rings than in diene **1**, which has only the cyano group on one of its phenyl ring. The Φ_f dramatically increases for all the dienes at lower temperature in the glassy matrix. For the substituted dienes, however, the Φ_f is far from unity though

Fig. 8. Fluorescence spectra of dienes **7** and **8** at (a) 298, (b) 77 K they increase to the maximum. This indicates that even at low temperatures the non-radiative transitions tend to decrease the fluorescence in substituted dienes. All the fluorescence spectra observed in rigid matrix at lower temperature are structured indicating absence of stabilizing effects of solvent polarity and molecular motions resulting in blue-shifted emission and increased fluorescence quantum yields.

Table 6. Fluorescence emission and excitation data for dienes DPB, **1**, **7** and **8** at 298 and 77 K in 1:1 (v/v) ethanol-methanol matrix

Diene	298 K			77 K		
	$\lambda_{f\max}$ nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f	$\lambda_{f\max}$ nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f
DPB	375	335	0.018	379	334	~1.0
1	418	347	0.007	412	328	0.500
7	416	333	0.005	417	333	0.401
8	478	357	0.006	436	360	0.509

N,N-Dimethylamino and cyanonitro substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes : Donor-acceptor DPB-compounds **9**-

12 show solvatochromic fluorescence behaviour similar to other donor-acceptor dienes described above (Tables 7 and 8). In general, the absorption λ_{\max} is not influenced much by solvent polarity. However, in a given solvent, the absorption λ_{\max} of the dienes vary in the order : **10** > **9** > **11** > **12**. Thus, among the four dienes, *para*-nitro-substituted diene **10** showed highest absorption maximum value of 440 nm, which is in accord with enhanced π -electron delocalization in the ground state

Table 7. UV-vis absorption spectral data for dienes **9**-**12**

Diene	Solvent ^a	λ_{\max}	$10^4 \epsilon$
		nm	dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
9	Cyclohexane	396	4.0
	THF	404	4.1
	MeOH	399	4.0
	MeCN	403	4.2
10	Cyclohexane	440	4.2
	THF	438	4.4
	MeOH	442	4.6
	MeCN	443	4.6
11	Cyclohexane	380	2.4
	THF	385	2.6
	MeOH	377	2.8
	MeCN	381	3.5
12	Cyclohexane	370	2.6
	THF	375	2.8
	MeOH	370	2.9
	MeCN	369	3.7

^aDielectric constant cyclohexane, 2.02, THF, 7.58, MeOH, 32.66, MeCN, 35.94

Table 8. Fluorescence spectral data for dienes **9**-**12**

Diene	Solvent	$\lambda_{f\max}$	Φ_f	λ_{ex}
		nm		nm
9	Cyclohexane	474	0.099	394
	THF	545	0.140	406
	MeOH	576	0.070	403
	MeCN	582	0.050	405
10	Cyclohexane	528	0.337	429
	THF	584	0.100	393
	MeOH	588	0.080	385
	MeCN	592	0.050	375
11	Cyclohexane	505	0.063	379
	THF	524	0.010	438
	MeOH	554	0.004	407
	MeCN	551	0.002	416
12	Cyclohexane	497	0.021	428
	THF	552	0.054	495
	MeOH	586	0.003	384
	MeCN	593	0.065	379

However, the $\lambda_{f\max}$ is greatly affected by the solvent polarity and a much red-shifted fluorescence is observed on increasing solvent polarity (Fig. 9). The $\lambda_{f\max}$ of the dienes in any given solvent, however, vary in the order : **10** > **9** > **11** > **12**. The absorption spectral data reveal that there is little difference in polarity between the ground state and

the initially prepared excited state. The fluorescence spectral data mean that the fluorescent state is not the same as the initially prepared excited state, and that it is more polar. The change in dipole moment ($\Delta\mu$) upon excitation as determined from Lippert-Mataga analysis is as follows : **9**, 11.6; **10**, 8.6, **11**, 8.2; **12**, 13.8 D. As compared to the other dienes mentioned in the above sections, these dipole moment changes are relatively smaller, indicating less polar character of the excited states of these dienes.

The time-resolved fluorescence decay curves were found to be of single exponential nature (Fig. 10). Though a biexponential fit to the decay curves was done to improve the chi square (χ^2 in the range of 0.9–1.1) values, the rela-

Fig. 9. (a) Fluorescence spectra of **9** in solvents of varying polarity : (1) cyclohexane, (2) tetrahydrofuran, (3) methanol and (4) acetonitrile. (b) Fluorescence spectra of **10** in solvents of varying polarity : (1) tetrahydrofuran, (2) methanol, (4) acetonitrile.

tive amplitude of the second or minor component was, however, found to be lesser than or equal to 10% in all cases. Thus, it can be said that the fluorescence originates from a single excited state species. For dienes, **9** and **10** the τ_f increases as the polarity of solvent is increased (Table 9). However, no such solvent polarity dependent increase in τ_f of dienes **11** and **12** was observed.

The effects of solvent polarity are also seen on the Φ_f of these dienes. In protic polar methanol, all the four dienes

Fig. 10. Fluorescence lifetime decay profiles of **9** and **10** in acetonitrile

have very low Φ_f . Except diene **12**, the other three dienes show a decrease in Φ_f with increase in solvent polarity. Also, Φ_f is the highest in *para*-nitro-substituted diene **10** in non-polar cyclohexane. In general, Φ_f of these dienes decreases with increase in solvent polarity. This observation is similar to the observation made earlier wherein it has been observed that Φ_f decreases monotonically as a function of solvent polarity for donor-acceptor systems³⁹. As mentioned above, the energy gap between A_u^* and B_u^* excited states in DPB is small and, hence, change in the molecular

Table 9. Fluorescence lifetime (τ_f) of dienes **9-12**

Diene	Solvent	τ_f ns
9	THF	0.37
	MeOH	0.57
	MeCN	0.61
10	THF	0.19
	MeCN	0.38
11	THF	0.65
	MeCN	0.69
12	THF	0.10
	MeOH	0.12
	MeCN	0.18

structure of the fluorophore or solvent orientation with respect to the fluorophore is expected to influence the level

ordering of the two excited states. Such changes might account for some variations in fluorescence and related excited state properties of various donor-acceptor dienes studied.

Thus, it is evident that electronic excitation of these donor-acceptor dienes is also accompanied by a considerable charge separation. The stability of the charge-separated species can be influenced by the internal mesomeric factors. The dienes are expected to be fully conjugated in the ground state; however, following excitation rotation of certain bonds can occur leading to the formation of conformationally relaxed charge transfer excited state. Thus, one possibility for explaining the large red shift and sensitivity of fluorescence to solvent polarity would be the participation of polar, conformationally twisted non-planar excited states. For the diene molecules, formation of such state should be possible by single bond rotation at several sites including carbon-carbon bond in the chain as well as C-N bonds in the aromatic ring. However, twisting of the C-C bond of dienyl moiety between the rings is not very likely, as it will require a relatively larger volume of activation. The initially excited state is most likely to be of B_{u}^+ nature, which is significantly influenced by the solvent polarity.

Photoisomerization of N,N-dimethylamino and cyano-nitro substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes : Direct irradiation of dienes **9-12** yields the corresponding 1*E*,3*Z*-isomer due to one-photon-one-bond photoisomerization (Table 10). The photoisomerization of *para*-substituted dienes **9** and **10** is more efficient than the photoisomerization of *meta*- or *ortho*-nitro-substituted dienes **11** and **12**. At photostationary state (PSS), 1*E*,3*E*-isomer dominates the photomixture. In general, the Φ_{PI} increases with increase in solvent polarity. However, such increase is more pronounced in case of dienes **11** and **12**. It is not very clear whether the photoisomerization occurs from the singlet or triplet excited state. It is known that triplet DPB can be formed by sensitized excitation⁵⁶. It has also been shown that the rate of intersystem crossing (ISC) decreases as the length of polyene chain increases⁵⁷. However, it has been reported that substitution of *trans*-1,2-diphenylethene by nitro group enhances the rate of ISC and leads to photoisomerization via triplet pathway. Additionally, highly solvent dependent mixed singlet-triplet mechanisms are observed in the photoisomerization of donor-acceptor diphenylethenes^{31,56-58}. In the present donor-acceptor dienes it is observed that the Φ_{PI} increases with concomitant decrease in Φ_{f} with respect to increasing solvent polarity. Further, it is also observed that the Φ_{PI} are higher in comparison to the Φ_{f} in any given solvent. These obser-

vations suggest that the fluorescence and photoisomerization processes compete with each other and singlet excited states can be involved in the photoisomerization process of these donor-acceptor dienes. It may, however, be noted that since the observed Φ_{PI} are generally low in many cases and are on the order of the triplet yields, there is the possibility of triplets contributing to the observed isomerization.

Table 10. Photostationary state (PSS) composition and quantum yield of isomerization (Φ_{PI}) for dienes **9-12** under direct irradiation condition

Diene	Solvent	% PSS composition		Φ_{PI}
		<i>E,E</i>	<i>E,Z</i>	
9	Cyclohexane	88	12	0.42
	MeOH	80	20	0.49
	MeCN	75	25	0.54
10	Cyclohexane	85	15	0.38
	MeOH	76	24	0.45
	MeCN	70	30	0.52
11	Cyclohexane	95	5	0.05
	MeOH	88	12	0.08
	MeCN	85	15	0.15
12	Cyclohexane	90	10	0.11
	MeOH	84	16	0.15
	MeCN	80	20	0.21

An increase in Φ_{PI} with increasing solvent polarity also suggests that a twisting motion around the double bond is more favored in polar media. A dipolar perpendicular species (P^*), which is stabilized in a polar solvent, can be precursor to the photoisomers. Also, such a polar excited state intermediate is more stabilized if formed at the double bond closer to the acceptor side of the molecule. Thus, *N,N*-dimethylarylidene [*N,N*-Me₂-Ar-CH=CH-] moiety acts as electron donating group and nitroarylidene [O₂N-Ar-CH=CH-] moiety acts as electron withdrawing group across the C=C double bond undergoing isomerization. The perpendicular excited state formed from such a substituted C=C double bond will be the most stabilized by electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups. The position of substituents on the aromatic ring affects the photoisomerization more than the type of substituents. Thus, *para*-substituted dienes **9** and **10** undergo more facile isomerization than the *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted dienes **11** and **12**. An increase in solvent polarity is also expected to reduce the activation barrier to the formation of highly polar perpendicular excited states. For maximum stabilization of energy, these states can have geometry that deviates from co-planarity. The twisting of carbon-carbon double bond between C3-C4 (near acceptor phenyl group) is favored over the twisting of carbon-carbon double bond between C1 and C2 carbons. The polar intermediate formed due to twisting of C3-C4 double bond may be more stable, hence preferred isomerization giving 1*E*,3*Z* isomer.

The other isomer (i.e. 1Z,3E) may not be formed due to relative instability of the corresponding twisted species. Thus, the regioselective photoisomerization occurs due to selective stabilization of the polar perpendicular species across one of the double bond in the diene moiety. These aspects of the excited states including possible structures of the intermediates involved in photoisomerization and fluorescence of these donor-acceptor dienes are depicted in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Possible intermediates involved in the photoprocesses of dienes 9-12.

N,N-Dimethylamino and carboxymethyl substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes: In contrast to nitro-substituted DPB compounds mentioned in the earlier sections, *N,N*-dimethylamino and carboxymethyl substituted-DPB compounds such as **15** exhibit very interesting fluorescence with relatively higher Φ_f in both polar, aprotic as well as in polar, protic solvents. We have recently synthesised donor-acceptor DPB compounds **13-15** and investigated their absorption and fluorescence properties⁶². It has been found that similar to nitro-cyano dienes, in these dienes also a very moderate-red shift in the λ_{\max} occurs with increasing solvent polarity. The absorption spectrum of **13** is similar to DPB (which shows three absorption peaks at 315, 330 and 350 nm) with vibrational structures at 329, 344 and 362 nm. With increase in solvent polarity, vibrational resolution in the absorption spectrum of **13** is diminished. The dienes **14** and **15** do not show any vibrational structures in their absorption spectrum, which only broadens with increase in solvent polarity. Among the three dienes, the disubstituted diene **15** shows the largest λ_{\max} (388 nm in heptane and 405 nm in DMF) which is due to the increased mesomeric effects of the two substituents.

The fluorescence spectrum of **15** is presented in Fig.

Fig. 12. Fluorescence spectra of **15** in (I) organic solvents: (a) *n*-heptane, (b) 1,4-dioxane, (c) tetrahydrofuran, (d) methanol, (e) acetonitrile, (f) dimethylformamide; (II) 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures: % of water in 1,4-dioxane is: (a) 0, (b) 10, (c) 20, (d) 30, (e) 40, (f) 50.

12. A red-shift of 120 nm in $\lambda_{f\max}$ of **15** is observed when the solvent is changed from *n*-heptane to methanol. As the polarity of solvent is increased, the Φ_f of **13** ($\Phi_f = 0.19$ in heptane; 0.01 in methanol) and **14** ($\Phi_f = 0.12$ in heptane; 0.03 in methanol) decrease but for **15** ($\Phi_f = 0.01$ in heptane; 0.12 in methanol) it increases. Diene **15** shows relatively large Φ_f even in protic, polar solvent like methanol, in which nitroaryldienes are known to have very low Φ_f ⁴⁶.

All the three dienes show linear correlation with solvent polarity parameters like $E_T(30)$ and π^* . From the slope of the plots of $\lambda_{f\max}$ vs $E_T(30)$ and π^* , it is inferred that the excited state of **15** is much more sensitive to solvent polarity than the other two dienes and hence it can be said that the excited state of **15** is much more polar than the ex-

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cited states of **13** and **14**. The excited state dipole moment change ($\Delta\mu$) determined using Lippert-Mataga plots for these dienes are as follows : **13**, 13.5; **14**, 20.1 and **15**, 28.4 D. A rather large value of $\Delta\mu$ for **15** indicates that its fluorescent state is dipolar in nature.

At 77 K in ethanol-methanol matrix, all the three dienes exhibit a blue-shifted $\lambda_{f\max}$ and an increased Φ_f . As compared to room temperature value, the largest blue-shift in $\lambda_{f\max}$ at lower temperature is observed for **15** ($\Delta\lambda_{f\max} = 84$ nm) and the highest increase in Φ_f (~25 times) is observed for **13**. Very large change in the excited state dipole moment (28.35 D), large red-shift and much greater sensitivity of fluorescence to solvent properties can be due to the participation of a conformationally twisted non-planar and highly polar excited state in the fluorescence of **15**. Thus, fluorescence of **15** in non-polar and polar solvents can be attributed to locally excited planar and conformationally relaxed non-planar charge transfer excited states respectively.

The formation of conformationally relaxed non-planar charge transfer excited state is possible by bond rotation at a number of sites including the carbon-carbon bonds between the aromatic centers as well as the C-N bond between the dialkylamino group and the aromatic ring. From the studies of systems without nitro substituent and in which one or more single and double bonds are selectively bridged it has been proposed that the bond connecting dimethylanilino group to the ethylenic double bond is responsible for twisting and formation of twisted excited state⁶³. As the twisting of a single bond connecting aryl group to the chain double bond requires larger reaction volume, it is likely that the twisting of single bond connecting *N,N*-dimethylamino group to aromatic ring (i.e. >N-Ar) is responsible for the formation of charge transfer state in **15**. The results of fluorescence studies at 77 K also support the above inference. In rigid matrix at 77 K, molecular motions in the fluorophores are expected to be absent. This will result in minimization of the solvent effects on the excited states of the dienes. As discussed in the previous sections, in the absence of solvent effects, blue shift in $\lambda_{f\max}$ of polar excited states is expected. Further, at low temperature, non-radiative transitions are expected to be minimum, hence increase in Φ_f . Molecular (bond) twists in **15** are inhibited in glassy matrix at lower temperature and hence emission occurs from its planar locally excited state.

Based on the results of fluorescence and photoisomerization studies of various donor-acceptor compounds mentioned above, probable pathways and steps for deactivation of the excited singlet state of these donor-acceptor diarylbutadienes are shown in Figs. 13 and 14. The diene

denoted as DADPB upon excitation first forms the delocalized excited state [DADPB^{*}_(DE)] which is stabilized by the solvent surrounding it leading to the formation of the planar intramolecular charge transfer state [DADPB^{*}_(ICT)]. This ICT state undergoes further stabilization after molecule has twisted out of planarity to form the conformationally relaxed state [DADPB^{*}_(TICT)] from which the much red-shifted fluorescence eventually occurs. The twisted excited state [DADPB^{*}_(TICT)] can be in equilibrium with the perpendicular state [DADPB^{*}_(P)] of the diene due to low activation barrier between the two states. This provides another pathway for deactivation of the excited singlet state and this can explain the low Φ_f . The photoisomerization to *1E,3Z*-isomer can occur via the perpendicular species [DADPB^{*}_(P)].

Fig. 13. Possible deactivation pathways for singlet excited state of dienes 9-12.

Thus, the photoprocesses of donor-acceptor dienes involve formation of delocalized π,π^* excited state that gets

Fig. 14. Steps involved in the photoprocesses of dienes 9-12. EE : ground state S_0 of the *trans, trans*-diene; EZ : ground state S_0 of the *trans, cis*-diene; DE : delocalized singlet excited state (S_1) having planar geometry; ICT : intramolecular charge transfer excited state (S_1), planar; TICT : conformationally twisted intramolecular charge transfer excited state (S_1), non-planar; P* : double bond twisted perpendicular species.

stabilized by non-radiative methods to an intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) state. Depending on the polarity of the medium and solvent reorganization the ICT state can decay to a conformationally relaxed non-planar twisted excited state. This twisted state can be dipolar in nature and hence it is stabilized in polar media yielding highly red-shifted fluorescence. The photoisomerization can occur from the polar perpendicular species (P*) that can exist in equilibrium with the planar as well as the conformationally twisted non-planar excited state depending on the

electronic effects of the substituents and the polarity of the solvent.

Fluorescence probe properties of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes

In recent years, there has been a lot of interest in developing probes and sensing systems. Many sensing mechanisms involve fluorescence properties and in this context several fluorescence probes have been developed and employed to characterize the microenvironment of organized assemblies. Very informative discussions on fluorescence probes and related sensing mechanisms can be found in several excellent publications, and only a few of them are cited here^{41,64-79}. The solvatochromic fluorescence behavior of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes prompted us to examine the fluorescence characteristics of these dienes in organized assemblies of micelles. Micelles are only too well known to be described here in any detail. Excellent account of micelles can be seen in Refs. 75-77.

In view of the above, we have investigated the fluorescence behaviour of dienes **1-8** and **15** in SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 micelles and used the resulting fluorescence properties to characterize the microenvironment of the micelles in terms of their micropolarity, probe solubilization site and CMC. It has been inferred that donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes can serve as good fluorescence probes for characterizing the microenvironment of micelles. Thus, some of the donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes can find applications as reporters of the microenvironment of organized assemblies and biological macromolecules. The results of this study are presented in the following sections.

Fig. 15. Plots of dielectric constants of 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures vs fluorescence λ_{fmax} of DPB and 1-6 in 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures: (o) DPB, (*) 1, (●) 2, (Δ) 3, (□) 4, (▲) 5, (×) 6.

Determination of micropolarity (dielectric constant) and probe solubilization site of micelles using nitrocyano dienes:

Fluorescence properties of donor-acceptor dienes **1-6**

have been employed to characterize the microenvironment of micelles in terms of dielectric constant of the micelle-water interface, diene solubilization site in micelles, and the CMC. Absorption and fluorescence data of **1-6** in SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 micelles are summarized in Table 11. In a given micelle, λ_{max} and λ_{fmax} of DPB, **1** and **3** do not change much. However, for **2, 4-6** charge-dependent shift of absorption and λ_{fmax} is observed. This indicates that the fluorophores occupy interfacial region, which may be due to the presence of polar nitro substituents.

Table 11. Absorption and fluorescence spectral data of DPB and dienes **1-6** in micelles

Diene	Media ^a	λ_{max} nm	λ_{fmax} nm	λ_{ex} nm	Φ_f
DPB	CTAB	323	400	329	0.094
	SDS	332	402	331	0.077
	Tri-X-100	331	400	332	0.127
1	CTAB	347	428	364	0.054
	SDS	350	426	360	0.045
	Tri-X-100	348	423	350	0.150
2	CTAB	395	603	399	0.037
	SDS	389	612	394	0.012
	Tri-X-100	397	538	402	0.016
3	CTAB	350	421	364	0.005
	SDS	347	434	360	0.007
	Tri-X-100	348	424	360	0.002
4	CTAB	363	548	375	0.014
	SDS	382	585	381	0.050
	Tri-X-100	372	544	377	0.011
5	CTAB	399	581	362	0.008
	SDS	389	610	385	0.010
	Tri-X-100	394	535	380	0.006
6	CTAB	362	557	381	0.005
	SDS	378	596	385	0.035
	Tri-X-100	378	500	392	0.004

^a $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$; Tri-X-100 is Triton-X-100

Since the solvatochromic fluorescence properties of the dienes were to be used to probe micellar environments, it was necessary to ensure that the fluorescence emission in surfactant solution is not due to any specific interaction between the diene and water molecules. The low solubility of dienes in water prohibits direct spectroscopic study in aqueous solution. Therefore, we examined electronic spectra of these dienes in 1,4-dioxane-water mixture, which have been discussed earlier. It was observed that for dienes **2, 4-6** the fluorescence gets highly red-shifted as the water content in the solvent mixture is increased. Since the relative dielectric constant of 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures is known⁵⁹, the λ_{fmax} of dienes DPB and **1-6** were plotted against the dielectric constant of the solvent to conclude that the λ_{fmax} of fluorescence of these dienes is governed by the bulk dielectric constant (ϵ) of the medium (Fig. 15). Using dienes **2, 4-6**, the dielectric constants (Table 12) of micelle-water interface in SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 micelles was determined by perusal of Fig. 15 and comparing it with the λ_{fmax} of the dienes in micellar solutions. Table 12 also gives the dielectric constant of these micelles as determined by some other well known probes like

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pyrene carboxaldehyde⁸⁰, *p*-*N,N*-dialkylaminobenzylidene malonitrile⁸¹ and ANS⁷⁵. The polarity of the interface is dependent on the nature of the head groups and it is increasing from nonionic to cationic to anionic micelles. The decrease in dielectric constant of the micelle-water interface compared to that of bulk water is due to the restrictive effect of the micellar surface charge on water molecules in the stern layer.

Table 12. Dielectric constant (ϵ) and critical micelle concentration (CMC) of micelles as determined using probe dienes 2, 4-6 and some other known probes*

Diene	Media	Calc.	CMC
		ϵ	M
2	CTAB	22	4×10^{-3}
	SDS	28	3×10^{-2}
	Triton-X-100	4	-
4	CTAB	9	9×10^{-4}
	SDS	27	9.5×10^{-3}
	Triton-X-100	8	-
5	CTAB	7	4×10^{-3}
	SDS	45	6×10^{-3}
	Triton-X-100	5	-
6	CTAB	16	4×10^{-3}
	SDS	45	7×10^{-3}
	Triton-X-100	10	-
Py-CHO	CTAB	36	9×10^{-4}
	SDS	40	8×10^{-3}
	Triton-X-100	28	3×10^{-4}
DABMN	CTAB	36	7×10^{-4}
	SDS	40	8×10^{-3}
	Triton-X-100	28	3×10^{-4}
ANS	CTAB	36	9×10^{-4}
	SDS	25	9×10^{-3}
	Triton-X-100	35	3×10^{-4}

*Py-CHO = pyridine carboxaldehyde; DABMN = dimethylaminobenzylidene malonitrile; ANS = anilino naphthalene sulfonic acid.

The results in Table 11 show that the Φ_f of 2, 4-6 in micelles of various surfactants are larger than those in non-polar solvents. Since we already showed that there is increase in Φ_f with increase in solvent polarity of the medium, the increase in Φ_f in micelles is attributable to the greater polarity of the micellar environment localizing the probe diene. The dielectric constant values calculated for 2, 4-6 in different micelles are more than that of hydrocarbons ($\epsilon = \sim 2$) and less than that of bulk water ($\epsilon = \sim 80$). The intermediate range of dielectric constant values suggests that the diene fluorophores are located in the interfacial region of the micelles. Slight changes in the dielectric constant values to that of previously reported values can be attributed to the structural differences in various fluorophores which can locate differently in the micellar systems. For compounds 2 and 4, which do not have any substituent on the diene moiety, the dielectric constants are observed to be low as compared to that of 5 and 6 in all the three micelles studied. This shows that 2 and 4 are most likely to be incorporated between hydrophobic alkyl chains with relatively more polar nitro group towards interfacial region. On similar grounds, it is inferred that dienes 1 and

Fig. 16. Plot of fluorescence λ_{\max} of CTAB- and SDS-constituted 2 and 4 vs surfactant concentrations : (o) CTAB, (●) SDS.

3 occupy the hydrophobic regions of the micelles.

Determination of CMC of the micelles using nitrocyano dienes : We have employed fluorescent dienes 2, 4-6 to determine the CMC for SDS and CTAB. In Triton-X-100, since no change in $\lambda_{f \max}$ of the four probe dienes with increasing concentration of the surfactant was observed, studies were done only in SDS and CTAB micelles. As a typical example, the dependence of fluorescence $\lambda_{f \max}$ of dienes 2 and 4 on surfactant (SDS and CTAB) concentrations is shown in Fig. 16. The calculated CMC values are given in Table 12. The $\lambda_{f \max}$ of the probe dienes in CTAB and SDS is constant over a narrow range of concentrations, which can be taken as the CMC of the surfactants. These CMC values are in fair agreement with the CMC values obtained by using other known probes^{59,78,80,81}. Below the CMC of SDS and CTAB, there is blue-shift in $\lambda_{f \max}$ for all the four probe dienes (2, 4-6). However, above the CMC of SDS and CTAB, dienes 4-6 exhibited blue-shifted fluorescence, while for diene 2, no shift in $\lambda_{f \max}$ was observed above CMC in the two micelles. This can be attributed to the interaction between monomeric surfactant with probe molecules and to the presence of premicellar aggregates. Slightly above the CMC range, there is change in fluorescence wavelength and it is observed to be constant for very high concentrations of the surfactants used. Thus, this change in the fluorescence wavelength can be attributed to the change in shape of the micelle with increase in surfactant concentration. It is known that in the vicinity of the CMC anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactant micelles are

mostly approximate to spheres but with increase in total concentration micelles become asymmetric⁷⁶. In Triton-X-100, the $\lambda_{f \max}$ is smaller as compared to that in ionic SDS and CTAB. For example, diene **2** in SDS shows fluorescence at 612 nm and in Triton-X-100 at 538 nm. Further, no change in $\lambda_{f \max}$ with increasing concentration of Triton-X-100 was observed for probe dienes **2**, **4-6**. These observations suggest that the excited states of probe dienes are affected by ionic micelles much more than the neutral micelles like Triton-X-100. Thus, donor-acceptor dienes **2**, **4-6** can serve as good fluorescence probes for microenvironment of charged micelles.

Fluorescence probe properties of cyanomethoxy dienes :

It is found that the dienes substituted with groups such as methoxy or cyano do not exhibit solvent polarity dependent large changes in their fluorescence maximum, thereby limiting their use⁴⁷. It has further been observed that for monosubstituted dienes bearing either a donor (e.g. OMe) or an acceptor (e.g. CN) group on the phenyl ring, while changing surfactant concentration does not significantly affect the probes' $\lambda_{f \max}$, significant change in the fluorescence peak intensity of the probe diene occurs⁴⁷. Such concentration dependent changes in fluorescence intensity of disubstituted dienes bearing both a donor and an acceptor (e.g. OMe and CN) is not observed. However, for such substituted dienes, the fluorescence peak position (i.e. $\lambda_{f \max}$) changes with changing surfactant concentration. The, $\lambda_{f \max}$ in case of disubstituted diene and the fluorescence peak intensity in case of mono-substituted dienes could be utilized to probe the microenvironment of micelles.

We have thus investigated the fluorescence probe properties of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in the microheterogeneous media of SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 micelles and using these dienes, CMC and micropolarity of the micelles have been determined. The absorption and fluorescence spectral characteristics of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in organic solvents of different polarity have been discussed in earlier section. As compared to the homogeneous media of organic solvents, the micellar environment does not cause significant change in the absorption spectra of these dienes (Table 13).

Table 13. UV-vis absorption and fluorescence data of DPB and dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in microheterogeneous media of micelles

Diene	Media	Max. wavelength, nm			Φ_f
		Abs.	Em.	Ex.	
DPB	CTAB	334	381	331	0.148
	SDS	333	379	329	0.108
	Triton-X-100	334	381	331	0.166
1	CTAB	350	421	346	0.012
	SDS	350	421	346	0.007
	Triton-X-100	350	418	346	0.020
7	CTAB	343	417	337	0.022
	SDS	340	395	335	0.017
	Triton-X-100	343	399	338	0.042
8	CTAB	365	483	361	0.013
	SDS	361	484	358	0.008
	Triton-X-100	365	468	359	0.018

Only a very moderate red-shift in the absorption λ_{\max} of dienes **1** and **7** is observed. The absorption and fluorescence data for these dienes in various compositions of 1,4-dioxane-water are presented in Table 5. The increasing amount of water in dioxane does not alter the λ_{\max} of these dienes to any significant extent. Thus, in general, solvent polarity does not significantly affect the ground state of these dienes.

In the micellar media, diene **7** shows fluorescence peak at around 418–421 nm, similar to its fluorescence in polar solvents like methanol and acetonitrile. The fluorescence spectrum of diene **8** in CTAB is red-shifted but in SDS and in Triton-X-100, it is blue-shifted as compared to in polar organic solvents (Fig. 17). For diene **8**, as compared to non-polar organic solvents, the $\lambda_{f \max}$ is significantly red-shifted; however, as compared to in polar

Fig. 17. Fluorescence spectra of diene **7** in micelles of (a) CTAB, (b) SDS, (c) Triton-X-100.

solvents, the $\lambda_{f \max}$ is blue-shifted in Triton-X-100 micelles. In general, as compared to fluorescence of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** in non-polar *n*-heptane, in micellar media the fluorescence of these dienes is red-shifted; the maximum red-shift is observed for diene **8**. A comparison of the $\lambda_{f \max}$ of these dienes in polar organic solvent such as methanol with those in micelles reveals that roughly the dienes experience relatively polar environment in the micelles.

The Φ_f of these dienes is relatively higher in Triton-X-100 as compared to in either SDS or CTAB. The fluorescence efficiency is the least in SDS micelles for these dienes. The decrease in fluorescence efficiency as the substitution takes place suggests increased non-radiative transitions in the photoprocesses of diphenylbutadienes.

The Stokes' shift for diene **8** in polar homogeneous media of organic solvents such as dimethylformamide, acetonitrile and methanol is greater than that in micellar media. Among the three micelles studied, the least Stokes' shift is observed in neutral Triton-X-100. Thus, the fluores-

cence spectrum is most affected by ionic micelles of SDS and CTAB. This can be due to interactions between the micellar charges and the polar diene fluorophore. Thus, while diene **8** shows significant micelle-charge-dependent fluorescence peak shifts, dienes DPB, **1** and **7** do not show such marked changes in their fluorescence λ_{max} .

Micropolarity and CMC of SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 micelles as probed by cyanomethoxy substituted diarylbutadienes 1, 7 and 8 : Because of the lack of strong charge transfer fluorescence in mono-substituted-dienes **1** and **7**, we have used the changes in the fluorescence peak intensity of these dienes to determine the CMC and dielectric constant of the micelles incorporating the dienes. As mentioned earlier, the dielectric constant of micellar domains incorporating the dienes was determined by first investigating the fluorescence characteristics of these dienes in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures. Diene **8** shows maximum increase of about 61 nm in $\lambda_{\text{f max}}$ as the percentage of water is increased upto 60%. However, for a 60% water content dienes **1** and **7** show an increase of only about 15 ~ 19 nm.

Changing the composition of binary solvent mixtures is expected to bring about changes in the electrostatic solute/solvent interactions that can be analyzed in terms of Kirkwood function ($\epsilon - 1 / 2\epsilon + 1$)^{55,82} relating dielectric constant (ϵ) of the solvents. The Kirkwood correlation in terms of an electrostatic model is used to show that the energy associated with charge or a dipole varies according

Fig. 18. Variation of $\nu_{\text{f max}}$ of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** with Kirkwood function ($\epsilon - 1 / 2\epsilon + 1$) for 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures : (i) 1,4-dioxane, (ii) 10% water in 1,4-dioxane, (iii) 20% water in 1,4-dioxane, (iv) 30% water in 1,4-dioxane, (v) 40% water in 1,4-dioxane, (vi) 50% water in 1,4-dioxane, (vii) 60% water in 1,4-dioxane.

Fig. 19. Variation of the fluorescence intensity of dienes **1** and **7** with surfactant concentration : (O) CTAB, (●) SDS.

to dielectric constant function. In order to describe such electrostatic solvent effects, we plotted fluorescence wavenumber ($\bar{\nu}_{\text{f max}}$) of dienes **1**, **7** and **8** vs Kirkwood parameter ($\epsilon - 1 / 2\epsilon + 1$) and the results are shown in Fig. 18. In all the three cases, a linear correlation is observed with the largest slope in case of diene **8** indicating more polar nature of its excited state. A comparative study of the fluorescence of micelle-incorporated diene **8** with that of 1,4-dioxane-water-incorporated diene **8**, revealed that the diene is located in the polar interfacial domain of the micelle especially for CTAB and SDS micelles. Since the $\lambda_{\text{f max}}$ of diene **1** in micelles is similar to that observed in polar methanol, it is further believed that these dienes are also located in the interfacial region, while diene **7** occupies a hydrophobic site especially in SDS and Triton-X micelles.

In case of dienes **1** and **7**, the CMC values were determined by using fluorescence intensities of the micelle-con-

stituted dienes. A plot of fluorescence intensity of micelle-constituted **1** and **7** against the varying concentration of the surfactants (CTAB and SDS) is shown in Fig. 19. For diene **8**, a plot of $\lambda_{f \max}$ of **8** in the micelles of SDS and CTAB vs varying concentration of the surfactants (CTAB and SDS) gave the CMC values (Table 14). The CMC values so obtained are in fair agreement with the CMC values reported in the literature^{59,75,80,81}. Since the CMC of micelles is also dependent on the stereo-electronic nature of the fluorophores, a slight variation in CMC values is only expected. Below the CMC, dienes **1** and **7** show structured fluorescence with significant increase in intensity in the pre-micellar region. The fluorescence intensity changes for monosubstituted dienes are predominant in ionic micelles, while in the micelles of Triton-X-100, the intensity changes observed do not show regular trend. Thus, diphenylbutadienes bearing relatively weak donor-acceptor substituents can act as probes in ionic micelles.

Table 14. Critical micelle concentration (CMC) of CTAB and SDS as determined using fluorescence of DPB and dienes **1**, **7** and **8**

Diene	Surfactant	CMC ^a mol dm ⁻³	ϵ
DPB	CTAB	1.10×10^{-3}	
	SDS	5.75×10^{-3}	—
	Triton-X-100	—	
1	CTAB	3.60×10^{-3}	18.0
	SDS	1.80×10^{-2}	18.0
	Triton-X-100	—	9.0
7	CTAB	3.00×10^{-3}	11.0
	SDS	2.10×10^{-3}	2.5
	Triton-X-100	—	2.0
8	CTAB	1.9×10^{-3}	19.0
	SDS	6.3×10^{-3}	19.5
	Triton-X-100	—	13.0

^aLit.^{59,78,80,81} CMC: CTAB, 9.4×10^{-4} ; SDS, 8×10^{-3} ; Triton-X-100, 2.4×10^{-4} .

Fluorescence probe properties of N,N-dimethylamino and carboxymethyl substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes :

Based on fluorescence studies of diene **15** in SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100, it has been inferred that this diene can act as good fluorescence probe to report the micropolarity of micellar domains. The fluorescence of diene **15** is significantly affected by the charges on the micelles. The $\lambda_{f \max}$ of **15** in CTAB (600 nm) and in SDS (596 nm) is red-shifted as compared to in Triton-X-100 micelles (546 nm). A comparison of $\lambda_{f \max}$ of the dienes in different micelles and in 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures (for which the dielectric constants are known) was used to obtain the polarity of micellar environment where the dienes are likely to be located. Fluorescence emission of **15** in CTAB corresponds to the $\lambda_{f \max}$ of the dienes obtained in 1,4-dioxane-40% water mixture and the CTAB micelle microenvironment in which the diene localize is found to have a dielectric constant of 25. Similarly, it was established that the dielectric constant of SDS microenviron-

ment incorporating **15** is also ~25. In Triton-X-100, however, **15** is located in micellar domain having dielectric constant of only about 5. Except in SDS, dielectric constants of micelle-water interface of CTAB and Triton-X-100 determined by using **15** are similar to that obtained by using nitrocyano dienes⁴⁶. Thus, the solvatochromic fluorescence properties of **15** can be used to probe the microenvironment of the micelle-water interface. Further work on fluorescence and fluorescence probe properties of N,N-dimethylaminocarboxymethyl dienes is in progress.

Summary and conclusions

The uv-vis absorption, fluorescence excitation and emission, solvent polarity parameter correlations of fluorescence, examination of excited state dipole moment changes, and photoisomerization studies of several donor-acceptor 1,4-diphenylbutadiene compounds have been undertaken. It has been found that the electronic nature of substituent and the solvent polarity can alter the relative positions of the lowest-lying π, π^* excited states (A_g^-/B_u^+) and change the shape of singlet excited state potential energy surface influencing fluorescence and photoisomerization dynamics of these dienes. It has also been found that in the photoprocesses of donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes are involved the initially prepared π, π^* delocalized, planar excited states that can get stabilized by non-radiative methods to a planar intramolecular charge transfer state. Further, depending on the polarity of the medium and solvent reorganization, the planar intramolecular charge transfer state can decay to a conformationally relaxed (across single bond) non-planar twisted excited state from which much red-shifted fluorescence can occur. The conformationally twisted non-planar intramolecular charge transfer state can be highly polar in nature. The photoisomerization can originate from a perpendicular dipolar species (the P* state, 90° twisted across ethylenic C=C double bond) that can exist in equilibrium with the planar intramolecular charge transfer as well as the conformationally twisted non-planar excited state, depending on the electronic effects of the substituents and the polarity of the solvent. Only one-photon-one-bond isomerization of the C=C double bond in the diene moiety closer to the acceptor group is observed. The donor-acceptor diphenylbutadienes have also been found to serve as good fluorescence probes for characterizing the microenvironment of micelles.

Besides being important in the photoprocesses of diphenylpolyenes, these results are relevant in understanding the excited states involved in light-induced biological energy and sensory transductions mediated by retinal-based photoreceptors. The retinylidene Schiff base chromophore in retinal-based photoreceptors has a strong acceptor group in form of the iminium ion (retinylidene-CH=NH⁺-protein). The extended polyene chain can act as a donor. Thus, the retinylidene Schiff base chromophore

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can be considered as a donor-acceptor system in which sudden polarization of charges in the excited state can lead to conformational and configurational relaxation via twisting of single/double bond(s). Thus, the involvement of twisted, dipolar, intramolecular charge transfer excited states in the photoprocesses of retinal-based photoreceptors mediating energy and sensory transductions is possible.

In conclusion it can be said that these photochemical and photophysical studies have brought out interesting features of the excited state structure and potential energy surface of linear polyenes. Additionally, these studies have provided new directions for the development of novel fluorescence probes based on linear polyenes.

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